

Optimal placement of FBG optical sensors on a composite scale glider for modal acquisition

D. Varricchio¹ , E. Del Priore² , P. Gaudenzi², Presenting L. Lampani²

*¹Demonstrators and Operational Missions for Earth Observation, Cira Italian Aerospace Research Centre, Via Maiorise 1
Capua, Italy,*

d.varricchio@cira.it

*²Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Sapienza University of Rome, Via Eudossiana 18 Rome, Italy,
emiliano.delpriore@uniroma1.it, paolo.gaudenzi@uniroma1.it, luca.lampani@uniroma1.it*

Objectives

- Development of a **modal-based Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)** system for an aeronautical structure aimed at the implementation and real-time update of a Digital Twin
- Target system → **CFRP scaled-glider**
- Deployment of a distributed **network of Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG)** sensors on the wings and fuselage
→ **Sensor placement optimization**

Carbon fiber/epoxy resin

Wingspan ≈ 3 [m]

Length $\approx 1,5$ [m]

Mass $\approx 2,920$ [K]

Numerical models, beyond the Digital Twin

SZD 55-1 Nexus

- Simplified scaled glider model
- 28 wing ribs
 - 2 main spars
 - 2 small spars
 - 20 fuselage frames
 - 6 tailplane ribs

- FE model
- 184,259 shell and beam elements
 - 181,478 nodes

Scaled FE model

Strain sensors

Benefit
Electromagnetic interference immunity
Reduced cabling issue
Multiplexing (N sensor on the same fiber)
Linearity in response over many orders of magnitude
Stability over time (no calibration required)
small size, light weight, embeddability

Drawback
Brittle
Critical bending radius (attenuation)
Cross Sensitivity (Temperature)

Sensor placement optimization – Objective Functions

Mode Visibility (Amplitude of response)

$$SR(\underline{x}_i^k) = \frac{\varepsilon_{sensor}(\underline{x}_i^k)}{\varepsilon_{max\ principals}^k} \quad \text{Sensor } i \text{ mode } k$$

$$\underline{x}_i^k = \begin{cases} \underline{x}_{G_i}^k & \text{Global coordinate centroid} \\ \underline{x}_{\theta_i}^k & \text{Global coordinate sensing direction vector} \end{cases}$$

- Always maximized respect to \underline{x}_i^k
- Minimum value chosen by user (Constraint)

Sensor placement optimization – Workflow

Sensor placement optimization – Modal Analysis

Elastic Mode Number	Natural freq. [Hz]
1	10.7750
2	26.2454
3	37.6160
4	46.3766
5	50.5324
6	76.3325
7	85.4584
8	90.2360

Sensor placement optimization – Validation

Optimization essentially based on maximization of amplitude \Rightarrow FBGs tends to be aligned with max/min principal deformation direction for a chosen point on the structure.

Check

Verify orientation FBG sensitivity direction respect the principal strain direction.

Verify if SR read by FBG is greater than the minimum value imposed in Optimization Tool.

Verification carried out on each sensor. Optimization consistent with constraint and assigned objectives

Mesh refined in the zone of sensors (same order of sensor length).

Strain sensor values are point measurements (sensors small compared to the structure).

$\varepsilon_x(\underline{x})$

$\varepsilon_y(\underline{x})$

$\gamma_{xy}(\underline{x})$

Strain at centroid of QUAD element if FBG center fall inside the element (strain \approx cost over element).

Strain at mesh node if FBG center fall on the fem node.

$$\varepsilon_{\eta}(\underline{x}) = \varepsilon_x(\underline{x})\cos^2\theta + \varepsilon_y(\underline{x})\sin^2\theta + \gamma_{xy}(\underline{x})\sin\theta\cos\theta$$

ϑ orientation of η direction respect to element QUAD reference .

Sensor placement optimization – FBGs CAD model

FBGs bonded in the inner part of skin

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Glider manufacturing

Fiber optic placement

Mark the position of sensors on wing upper skin
(Catia Unfold + 2D drawing)

Placement and bonding of sensors

Polymerization

Test well working of FBGs

Vibrational test setup

Experimental testing – Workflow

At the time of research FBG interrogator maximum sampling frequency about 100 Hz

⇒ Input force 0 – 50 [Hz] ⇒ only first four frequencies detectable

Experimental testing – Mode Shapes

44 accelerometric sensors placed on the structure to estimate mode shapes

Experimental testing – FFT & Examples FBG Sensitivity

FBG N° 12 fus anti-Optimized mainly for mode 2

FBG N° 10 wing Optimized mainly for mode 3

Experimental testing – FBG (OMA) vs Acc. (EMA)

- **Operational Modal Analysis** estimates the modal properties of a structure based on vibration data collected when the structure is under its operating conditions (**output only**), assuming the input is randomic
- Comparison reveals **close correspondence** between Experimental Modal Analysis using accelerometers and Operational Modal Analysis using FBGs

Natural Frequencies

Elastic Mode Number	Accelerometers [Hz]	FBGs [Hz]	FEM [Hz]
1	6.92	6.84	10.77
2	21.15	21.33	26.24
3	30.71	30.96	37.61
4	34.70	35.04	46.37

Modal Dampings

Elastic Mode Number	Accelerometers [%]	FBGs [%]	FEM [%]
1	8.69	8.96	-
2	2.21	2.88	-
3	1.87	1.50	-
4	1.68	1.92	-

Conclusions

A laboratory-scale system to study the structural monitoring of an aeronautical structure using an embedded sensor network, aimed at building a Digital Twin has been developed

What has been done:

- Realization of a numerical and experimental model of a scaled glider
- Definition of a strain-modes based procedure for the optimal placement of a network of FBG sensors
- Execution of experimental tests for correlation with numerical data

Next steps:

- Update of the finite element model through numerical-experimental tuning
- The updated model will enable virtual damage simulations and the implementation of predictive algorithms and shape sensing strategies within the Digital Twin framework

Ongoing developments:

- Design of real-time shape sensing algorithms based on inverse finite element techniques, which use strain data from FBG sensors to reconstruct the structural state of the system.

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Thank you for your attention